

**FORMATION OF MODERN APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT
OF MANAGERIAL SKILLS AND LEADERSHIP SKILLS OF STUDENTS
OF HIGHER EDUCATION ORGANIZATIONS**

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Abstract: The science of modern pedagogy develops guidelines for the comprehensive, diverse perspective of management ideas and their application in educational practice. It is impossible to imagine the solution of management problems in the process of higher education without the development of managerial skills, professional skills and leadership skills in students. The introduction of such an approach serves to prevent accidents and contingencies in management.

Key words:

The competency approach provides for the formation of professional competence and managerial qualities in future educators. A new teacher who comes to work after graduating from a higher education institution will find a place based on his / her potential, knowledge, managerial skills, and responsible approach to work. In some cases, the educators of the educational institution influence the young specialist. The aspiration, initiative or indifference, business acumen of educators in a team can affect a young educator. Assistant of teacher to the preschool have a different perspective until they understand the work of educators, their job responsibilities, their professional responsibilities, and the community environment. Young educators need to understand the importance of knowledge, skills and competencies in order to meet the requirements of the educational institution. The management style of managers also contributes to the positive potential of young professionals in the preschool education organization and their attitude to the profession. Young professionals study the team environment, analyze it in depth and plan their future activities. Our practical experience has shown that most young educators for a long time have difficulty adapting to the socio-psychological conditions in the organization of preschool education. Some young professionals are reluctant to pursue professional careers to work in other fields, despite their pedagogical ability to adapt to the community. The occurrence of such situations depends on various

reasons. In some preschools, principals and members of the teaching staff may not have a positive relationship with newcomer educators.

Instead of being happy and supportive of the young specialist's rapid gain in popularity and support among the community and students due to his research, knowledge, and interest in his subject, they complain that his experience is not enough. As a result of reprimanding and embarrassing young professionals in pedagogical councils, it causes them not to work in an educational institution. Young professionals have problems in organizing their professional activities due to insufficient development of experience, skills and competencies, as a result of which they are unable to adapt quickly to the team. Lack of timely methodological support by the head or teachers also reduces the workload given to them. The lack of methodological support and support for young educators prevents them from pursuing a professional career. The young specialist develops skills and competencies related to the field. The director of the educational organization should take a differential approach, taking into account the professional qualities and abilities of each teacher in the team, his responsibility for the work. Learns by observing the interaction of newcomers with the pedagogical team. Managers include in the annual work plan the study of the activities of young professionals and the provision of methodological advice, based on which they monitor their activities. This will be a means of organizing quality education in the community. As a result of studying the scientific literature and research, the following scientific recommendations were formed in order to develop management skills in preschool students. The potential of teachers in educational institutions is one of the most important criteria for increasing the ranking of directors of these institutions. Therefore, it is necessary to use teachers with high intellectual level, experience and skills, deep knowledge of their subject, creative and organized, to create a comfortable environment for them, to closely assist them to engage in scientific activities. based on the opinion of scientists, it can be concluded that competence is a person's ability to solve a particular problem based on existing knowledge and life experiences.

So, in our opinion, competence is a set of skills that a person needs not only professionally, but throughout his life. Without full mastery of them, no specialist can successfully carry out their pedagogical activity. Propose grouping of competencies on the basis of cluster approach as follows:

competencies in working with information: data collection and analysis, information processing;

competencies for success: planning, organization of activities, analysis of results;

From these considerations, we can conclude that the universally recognized nature of the concept of competence and a single classification of competencies has not been developed.

The main goal of educational reforms in our country is to train young professionals in a comprehensive, mature and educated way. A qualified specialist is a professional who is professionally and spiritually developed, able to plan the present and future, and contribute to the scientific development of society.

From these considerations, we can conclude that the universally recognized nature of the concept of competence and a single classification of competencies has not been developed. According to T. Kono, the manager should be an expert in engineering or social sciences. The socio-economic status of the leader is an important factor in management. Leaders of educational institutions are superior to other educators in their ability to find solutions to any socio-economic problems, social relations, intellectual potential, rich experience. In his initial activities, the leader enhances the socio-economic status of the organization. Gradually learns each member of the team individually and creates the necessary conditions. Family traditions also influence the development of management skills in a leader. Born into a family of leaders, mastering the parental experience evokes a tendency to dominance. A modern leader performs the functions of a manager, diplomat, leader, coach, innovator, all of which are within the professional competence of the manager.

1. The manager-leader This task is traditional and is managed. The leader-leader must be the right word, promising, highly professional, leading in relationships, communicative, communicative, supportive, pedagogical-psychological.

2. The diplomat-leader has been a widely accepted management component in recent times and is considered to be the most optimal form of negotiation among the team.

3. Leader. The organization manager carries out leadership work. American scientists recommend that every manager should be a leader. In their view, the task of leadership and leadership do not mean the same thing. To perform this task, the manager must have the ability to follow the educators, that is, be inclined to perform the role of leader.

Above we have substantiated the personal qualities of a manager that are important for effective management activities. This encourages future educators to form a manager and leadership in themselves. In the future, it will further enhance the management and ensure the achievement of the strategic goals of the organization.

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